

"THE ROLE OF UNBALANCED NUTRITION IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF DISEASES IN CHILDREN."

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Abstract: In recent years, there has been a sharp disruption in dietary trends among the population. As a result of the increasing occurrence of such situations, a decline in the consumption of animal fats, animal proteins (complete), macro and microelements, vegetables and fruits, as well as vitamins, has been observed, alongside a growing intake of refined food products. According to WHO experts, iron deficiency is considered the main risk factor in the development of iron deficiency anemia (IDA), which is associated with unbalanced or improper dietary practices and failure to adhere to the principles of rational nutrition.

Keywords: children's and adolescents' institutions, anemia, iron deficiency, vitamin deficiency, daily diet, vitamin insufficiency.

Аннотация: В последние годы наблюдается резкое нарушение пищевых тенденций среди населения. Вследствие увеличения таких ситуаций отмечается снижение потребления животных жиров, животных белков (полноценных), макро- и микроэлементов, овощей и фруктов, а также витаминов, наряду с растущим употреблением рафинированных продуктов питания. По мнению экспертов ВОЗ, дефицит железа считается основным фактором риска развития железодефицитной анемии (ЖДА), связанной с несбалансированным или неправильным питанием и несоблюдением принципов рационального питания.

Ключевые слова: учреждения для детей и подростков, анемия, дефицит железа, дефицит витаминов, ежедневный рацион, недостаточность витаминов.

Relevance of the Topic: The deficiency of proteins, fats, carbohydrates, minerals, and vitamins in the daily diet of children and adolescents in institutions creates conditions for the development of various disorders in their bodies. The deterioration of the ecological situation has led to the introduction of unwanted compounds into the body through food and water. The widespread use of antibiotics in livestock production has caused the emergence of new infections resistant to antibiotics and increased the incidence of hospital-acquired infections. According to WHO experts, iron deficiency anemia (IDA) is primarily caused by improper or unbalanced nutrition. All these factors significantly contribute to the risk of developing osteoporosis, obesity, overweight, hypertension, ischemic heart diseases, diabetes, allergies, and other illnesses by creating favorable conditions and opportunities for their occurrence.

Objective: To prevent diseases arising among all strata of the resident population, the study aims to understand the daily energy expenditure and health status of individuals according to their work activities, alongside the health status and periodic nutrition of mothers, the negative impact on fetal development, to study their healthy nutrition, develop necessary recommendations, and apply them in practice.

Research Materials: The study utilized data on the physical development of children and adolescents, their daily diet, blood parameters, morbidity rates of schoolchildren, survey results, health status, and anthropometric measurements.

Research Results: Among various layers of the resident population, the deficiency of meat and meat products, dairy products, fish and fish products, fruits, and vegetables in the daily diet, coupled with excessive consumption of bread and bakery products, causes various diseases. Vitamin deficiencies increase children's susceptibility to infectious and toxic factors, reducing their physical and mental performance. In Canada, 4-5% of non-indigenous preschool children suffer from iron deficiency anemia, while the prevalence among indigenous children and Inuit infants ranges from 13% to 23%. However, in developing countries, anemia prevalence reaches high levels; in some countries, this indicator exceeds 50% among children under one year old.

Scientific research shows that iron deficiency anemia is identified in 90% of cases among children. Up to 60% of children born from multiple pregnancies and one-year-

old infants also suffer from iron deficiency. Analysis of survey data revealed that mothers have insufficient knowledge about IDA (iron deficiency anemia).

The nutritional status, activity, and condition of children were tested using the Melbourne program's dietary, anthropometric, and socio-demographic data involving 485 infants (average age 9 months, SD 1.3) and 424 children (average age 20 months, SD 2.5), along with their mothers. The average iron intake was 9.2 mg/day (SD 4.3) for infants and 6.7 mg/day (SD 2.4) for children.

Our research shows that 32.5% of infants and 19.15% of children have inadequate iron intake. The main nutritional source of iron should be iron-fortified infant formulas and cereals specifically designed for infants and children.

It is important to emphasize that analyses conducted over the last decade indicate that among infants, preschoolers, schoolchildren, and subsequently the entire population, the prevention of anemia primarily depends on daily energy expenditure, knowledge of work activities, health status, maternal health and periodic nutrition, and their impact on fetal development and healthy nutrition.

Conclusion: The lack of knowledge among mothers of children born with anemia and iron deficiency anemia about anemia symptoms, the impact of food products (especially iron-rich foods) on the development of anemia, and parents' insufficient awareness about anemia issues require promoting a healthy lifestyle. Moreover, it is essential to propagate and instill healthy nutrition practices throughout the population.

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